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**A NEW PERITONEAL ADHESION INDEX (PAI-4GV/D)
IN THE CLASSIFICATION OF ABDOMINAL ADHESIONS
AND ITS ROLE IN DETERMINING THE RISK OF REOPERATION
ON LAPAROSCOPIC SURGERY**

Klyshbekov N. A.

Doctoral student

Astana Medical University, Astana, Republic of Kazakhstan;

Surgeon

*The Medical Centre Hospital of the President's Affairs Administration of
the Republic of Kazakhstan, Astana, Republic of Kazakhstan*

Fursov R. A.

Associate Professor

Astana Medical University, Astana, Republic of Kazakhstan;

Surgeon

*Main Military Clinical Hospital of the Ministry of Defense of the
Republic of Kazakhstan, Astana, Republic of Kazakhstan*

Fursov A. B.

Professor

Astana Medical University, Astana, Republic of Kazakhstan;

Surgeon

*National Coordination Center for Emergency Medicine of the Republic
of Kazakhstan*

Fedyanin S. D.

Professor, Surgeon

Vitebsk State Order of Peoples' Friendship Medical University,

Vitebsk, Republic of Belarus

Abstract. *Abdominal adhesions 'de novo' (following surgery for adhesive intestinal obstruction) represent an extremely undesirable complication for the patient. Adhesive connections in the abdominal cavity significantly complicate the work of surgeons, especially during repeat operations. This study utilized a scientific approach based on the concept of the so-called interface. The refined term 'adhesive interface' was proposed. Within this conceptual framework, a barrier mesogel was applied intraoperatively to prevent adhesion formation. An original*

proprietary classification of the abdominal adhesion index has been developed. Unlike the widely used Peritoneal Adhesion Index (PAI), the index proposed and validated by us includes 4 gradations and 2 additional zones to account for adhesion localization (V-Ventral zone and D — Dorsal zone). It was found that 'de novo' adhesion is more frequently detected in the ventral zone and less frequently in the dorsal zone. The peritoneal index scale proposed by us, named PAI-4gV/D, may assist in determining the method and site of trocar insertion into the abdominal cavity. Including in single-port surgery (Single-port surgery).

Keywords: *'de novo' adhesion, Peritoneal Adhesion Index, surgery, adhesiolysis, adhesion prevention*

Abdominal 'de novo' adhesions (following surgery for adhesive intestinal obstruction) are a common and highly undesirable complication for the patient. Such adhesive formations in the peritoneal cavity significantly complicate surgeons' work during subsequent reoperations. Serious complications following surgical intervention for acute intestinal obstruction (AIO) are always associated with significant treatment challenges and suboptimal efficacy. This remains an unresolved issue for surgeons, gastroenterologists, and other specialists.

We conducted a review and comprehensive analysis of the most recent medical literature, where the mechanisms of adhesion prevention are systematically discussed and reconsidered. Special attention was given to the clinical features of the disease, diagnostic methods, and treatments most commonly used in patients recently, which have been the focus of discussions and scientific debates.

Furthermore, the positive properties and drawbacks of anti-adhesive agents were thoroughly studied. After applying various prophylactic methods in our surgical practice and obtaining insufficiently reliable, and in some cases highly unconvincing, results, we realized that primary attention must be paid to the physicochemical characteristics of anti-adhesive drugs and devices.

Experience and observations of patients in the surgical clinic indicated the direction in which research should be conducted regarding the causes of failures in the prevention and treatment of abdominal adhesions.

By analyzing contemporary publications, what was quite obvious but had long seemed less important was clearly identified. At the same time, two components were distinguished within a single paradigm, within which the problem of adhesion formation should be comprehensively considered.

1. First and foremost, this involves understanding and formulating a concept based on the following: for a thorough analysis, biological, chemical, and morphological studies of adhesions must be conducted. Particularly those adhesions that form and newly develop at the tissue interface ('de novo' adhesion). This adhesion process occurs: a) between the walls of the intestine, b) between the intestinal wall

and the parietal peritoneum, and c) also between the walls of the intestine and adipose tissue, including the omentum.

2. Secondly, the necessity to adopt and take into account the conceptual framework that highlights the predominant role of the qualitative composition of the anti-adhesive agent. As well as the condition of organs and tissues (severity of the inflammatory process, presence of peritoneal damage, depth and extent of desiccation, etc.) in the initiation and progression of adhesions. It is also necessary to consider and classify the methods of applying anti-adhesive films, as well as other devices, which can be grouped under the term 'Anti-adhesive implant/components' (AntiAI). Unlike routine approaches focused on the quantitative and volumetric application of materials, the new concept, based on the analysis of the interaction between AntiAI and surrounding tissues, aims to study the earliest processes of adhesion development (adhesions 'de novo'), with the goal of enhancing anti-adhesive efficacy. We support the opinion of certain clinicians regarding the presence of different types of adhesions between tissues. Our research is based on the issue of the development of such events (adhesion formation) at the boundary between two anatomical regions. More precisely, on the fact that this process occurs in the transitional layer between two surfaces, that is, at the contact point, at the interface between two media. Recently, this boundary layer has been termed the 'Interface.' We propose to consider it in a more specific manner. Therefore, in our study, during the investigation of the formation of abdominal adhesions, we designated it as the 'Adhesive Interface.' Considering current scientific advances in adhesion prevention and the concept of the interface, we have divided the classification of adhesion prevention mechanisms into several principal types. These include antiproliferative, tissue growth reducing/suppressive, anti-inflammatory, anti-edematous, and antifibrotic types. They correspond to the primary determinants of anti-adhesion efficacy. In this context, the volumetric properties of the adhesion mechanism serve as the main auxiliary factors supporting the mechanism of adhesion formation and enhancing the interface functionality.

By volumetric properties, we refer to: a) mechanical strength, b) degradation kinetics, c) compliance of adhesions, and their extensibility. In our studies of adhesions, we adhere to the contemporary scientific concept that characterizes the pathogenesis of adhesion formation. It encompasses three principal processes induced by operative trauma: (I) inhibition of fibrinolytic and extracellular matrix degradation systems; (II) induction of the inflammatory response involving the production of cytokines and transforming growth factor- β (TGF- β 1), a key regulator of tissue fibrosis; (III) induction of tissue hypoxia following disruption of blood supply to mesothelial cells and submesothelial fibroblasts, leading to increased expression of *factor-1 α* induced by hypoxia and *vascular endothelial growth factor*, which is responsible for collagen formation and angiogenesis.[1]

We employed well-known approaches to adhesion prevention, such as modern surgical methods (surgical method — Surg), which are optimally adapted for the abdominal adhesion process; pharmacological/medicinal products (pharmacological/medicinal products — PhmP); Anti-adhesion films/forms, so-called AntiAI. To prevent abdominal adhesion during laparoscopic surgery, the anti-adhesion gel “Lintex/Mesogel” was used as a PhmP, which belongs to the barrier component of the scientific concept of the “interface” proposed by Zhen Zheng et al. in 2025. The more specific term ‘adhesive’ refers to the management of adhesion resulting from intraoperative injury or desiccation of organ surfaces during surgery. The action of the gel is intended to create a temporary barrier around (at the interface of) the injured contacting surfaces. This ensures their separation during the healing period.

To characterize the volume, nature, quantity, and severity of the adhesion process in the peritoneal cavity, the well-established Peritoneal Adhesion Index (PAI) classification was used. [2] This classification includes the following gradations: 0 — No adhesions; 1 — Filmy adhesions, blunt dissection; 2 — Strong adhesions, sharp dissection; 3 — Very strong vascularized adhesions, sharp dissection, damage hardly preventable. For the assessment, 10 adhesion locations are also presented, ranging from ‘Epigastrium’ to ‘Pelvis’ and ‘Bowel to bowel.’

PERITONEAL ADHESION INDEX:

Regions:	Adhesion grade:
A Right upper	___
B Epigastrium	___
C Left upper	___
D Left flank	___
E Left lower	___
F Pelvis	___
G Right lower	___
H Right flank	___
I Central	___
L Bowel to bowel	___

However, our experience with the use of the aforementioned adhesion index over 10 years has revealed the necessity for its improvement. In our study, it was determined that obtaining a comprehensive overview of the adhesion process in a significant number of patients using PAI is challenging. Characterizing all adhesion localization sites in the abdominal cavity and their quality is quite difficult. It has been found that adhesions between the anterior abdominal wall and the intestine, as well as the greater omentum, impede not only the introduction of the trocar but also an adequate laparoscopic surgery with adhesiolysis. Analysis of clinical cases has shown that the nature and density of anterior adhesions differ from those of posterior adhesions (formed between the intestine and the posterior leaf of the parietal peritoneum). When such adhesions predominate, the introduction of trocars into the abdomen is not impeded, and ‘de novo’ adhesion at these sites is minimal according to our data.

According to our observations of 148 laparoscopic adhesiolysis surgeries, in 73 (49%) cases, the insertion of two or three trocars at different sites was extremely difficult. Therefore, we opted for a transumbilical single-port access to the abdominal cavity through a single incision, known as Single-port surgery (SpSurg). In the other cases, the access was traditional (3-port) or via open laparotomy. During the postoperative period, recovery was more favorable in patients with posterior (dorsal) localization of adhesions.

The dorsal zone — **D** (from Latin *dorsalis*) induced “de novo” adhesions less frequently than the ventral zone — **V** (from Latin *ventralis*). However, during reoperation, the localization of these adhesions was predominant. Complications such as acute intestinal obstruction were very rare, not exceeding 10% within 1 year. In contrast, for ventral localization, the incidence of intestinal obstruction was observed in 23% of patients after 1 year.

We considered this phenomenon in subsequent surgeries. Furthermore, reoperation using the single-port surgery (SpSurg) method demonstrated a minimal risk of injury to internal organs (intestine, omental vessels, etc.), since in those same patients with D localization of adhesions, the peritoneal adhesion index was lower. This risk cannot be calculated using the traditional PAI. In our developed PAI classification (with a 4-point grading scale considering ventral and dorsal zones), this issue was resolved quite successfully. The scheme of the developed and validated «Peritoneal Adhesion Index» is presented in

Figure 2. Peritoneal Adhesion Index — PAI-4gV/D; where V-Ventral zone (lat. ventralis); D — Dorsal zone (lat. dorsalis), separated by a vertical line.

The classification developed by us: «Peritoneal Adhesion Index — 4-grade V/D»

- 0 — No adhesions.
 - 1 — Filmy adhesions, blunt dissection.
 - 2 — Dense adhesions, sharp + blunt dissection.
 - 3 — Very dense vascularized adhesions, sharp dissection only.
 - 4 — Very dense vascularized adhesions, where injury is difficult to prevent.
- Regions A, B, C, D, E, F, G, I, H are supplemented by two zones: V and D.

As a result. For example, if there is a single dense adhesion **2g** located in region **H** supplemented by zone **D**, the index notation for the identified adhesion during surgery will be: **2gH/D**. If an adhesion **2g** is localized in region **H**, in the anterior ventral zone, then the adhesion designation according to our index will be **2gH/V**.

The adhesion index developed by us and presented in this article is highly practical for the surgeon's work; it is more precise and more universal compared to the index currently used worldwide. It is especially essential when deciding whether to perform surgery using the SpSurg method.

Conclusions. The study of the mechanisms of 'de novo' adhesion formation requires a new approach to the conceptualization of the so-called 'Adhesive Interface'. The analysis of various preventive methods and the development of new techniques should be undertaken within this new paradigm. This fundamentally proposes an approach to the prevention of adhesion formation within the framework of an anti-adhesive strategy aimed at preventing tissue fusion at the interface between two environments. In our study, the newly proposed classification

of abdominal adhesions, PAI-4gVsDs (comprising 4 gradations and two zones), enables an accurate characterization of abdominal adhesions, including their localization and nature. The primary advantage of our enhanced PAI-4gVsDs index is its capability to determine the risk of possible intestine injury during reoperation and the insertion of a laparoscopic trocar. The presence of a large number of adhesions-Vs (according to PAI-4gVsDs) indicates the necessity of performing single-port transumbilical access using the Single-port surgery technique.

References

1. Zhen Zheng, Shengli Gao, Jingwen Liu, Yong Zhang. *Interface before bulk: Mechanism-informed strategy for preventing postoperative adhesion based on polymer implants. Acta Biomaterialia. 2025; V.206: P. 43-73. doi: 10.1016/j.actbio.2025.09.021*
2. Coccolini F, Ansaloni L, Manfredi R, Campanati L, Poiasina E, Bertoli P, Capponi MG, Sartelli M, Di Saverio S, Cucchi M, Lazzareschi D, Pisano M, Catena F. *Peritoneal adhesion index (PAI): proposal of a score for the “ignored iceberg” of medicine and surgery. World J Emerg Surg. 2013 Jan 31;8(1):6. doi: 10.1186/1749-7922-8-6*

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